

Strengthen of Cold-Formed Steel Column with Ferrocement Jacket: Push out Tests

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Abstract—The population growth in the world requires an increase in demand of residential and housing construction. Using lightweight construction materials such as cold formed steel sections and ferrocement could be an alternate solution to foster the construction industry. In this study, a new composite column is introduced. It consists of cold formed steel section and ferrocement jacket. The ferrocement jacket was constructed using self-compacting mortar with two wire steel mesh of 550 MPa yield strength. Experimental push out tests was conducted to investigate the strength capacities and behavior of proposed shear connectors namely, bolt, bar-angle and self-drilling screw shear connectors. It was found that bolt connector showed the best behavior followed by bar-angle. Also, it was concluded that the ferrocement could be used to strength and improve the behavior of cold formed steel column.

Keywords—Cold formed steel, composite column, push out test, shear connector, ferrocement, strengthen method.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE traditional construction materials such as steel and concrete have exhibited signs of deterioration over the years in their long-term performance, which can be attributed to either the inherent nature of the materials or the weak resistance offered by these materials to adverse environmental conditions and natural disasters such as fires and earth quakes. In addition, retrofitting or rejuvenation of structures composed of such materials requires the use of skilled labors, heavy equipments, excessive energy and time which results in the escalation of the overall cost. Recent evaluation of the civil engineering infrastructure has demonstrated that most of it will need major repairs in the near future.

The maintenance of under-strength or deteriorated steel structures has been a subject of concern for structural engineers for decades. Major causes of distress or premature deterioration pertaining to steel structures include improper design or construction of the structure, changes in the structural function, and modifications in the load specification, corrosion of the steel, and exposure to impact or fire. When the structural member is a steel column, concrete jacketing, by encasing the existing steel section in a reinforced concrete jacket, is a commonly used technique.

Despite wide application of concrete jacketing in strengthening the steel columns of existing structures, research on the jacketing of such cold-formed steel columns is still in the early stages. From the last century, concrete jackets have

been provided primarily to serve as protection against corrosion and fire [1], and thus were assumed not to resist structural loading. With present-day modern steel-concrete composite construction techniques, the stiffness and strength gain effects have been taken into account for steel columns strengthened with concrete jackets.

The use of ferrocement as an external jacket to cold-formed column is investigated in this study. Ferrocement is a special form of reinforced concrete, which exhibits a behavior differing much from conventional reinforced concrete in strength performance and potential application. Therefore, the uniform dispersion of reinforcement in the matrix offers in achieving improvement in many of the engineering properties of the material, such as tensile and flexural strength, toughness, fracture, crack control, fatigue resistance and an impact resistance and in addition it also provides advantages in fabrication [2]. In developing countries, the raw materials for ferrocement construction are easily available, and also it could be constructed in any complicated shape. The skill required is of low level and it has superior strength properties as compared to conventional reinforced concrete [3]–[7]. It was proven that, jacketing with rounded corner give certain degrees of confinement by reducing stress concentration at corners [8], [9]. This justifies the development of innovative rehabilitation and strengthening method by ferrocement jacket for cold-formed steel structures. The development of innovative rehabilitation and strengthening technique is required to extend the life expectancy of many steel structures and limited studies were reported for the similar work in case of ferrocement strengthened cold-formed column.

Stud (or bolt) connectors are subjected to flexural and axial forces in resisting the interface forces by means of dowel action. Force transfers in composite structures depend on the strength and stiffness of various components of the composite beam as well as shear connectors. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the design parameters namely, shear strength and stiffness for stud connector prior to their use in construction. This task is mostly accomplished by conducting experiments on push-out specimens. Several types of push-out specimens have been studied in past decades and reported in the literature. Behaviour of stud shear connectors in light weight and normal weight concrete is studied by Al-Salloum [10]. Investigation on the strength of push-out specimens have been carried out by Ollgard [11]. Later, Hawkins [12] has recommended various empirical equations to include the effect of variation in material strength, on the strength of shear connectors. Effect of transverse reinforcement on the shear

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III. TEST RESULTS

All tests results are summarized in Table I. The load-slip curves are shown in Fig. 4. The failure mode of all test specimens could be attributed to the failure of the shear connectors. The specimen resisted the applied load in elastic manner up to about 80% from the ultimate load. However, the specimen showed plastic behavior in a very limited range before the failure where the shear connector was sheared-off. Longitudinal cracks were observed on the ferrocement jacket at early stage of loading and become wider as load increase. Fig. 5 shows the failure mode of the specimens.

According to the test results, the load slip responses of all specimens seem to exhibit a similar pattern. It can be observed from Fig. 4, that specimen with shear connector of 10 mm bolt showed better resistance to the applied load and more ductile behavior as compared to bar-angle and self-drilling screw shear connectors with an improvement up to 45%. However, self-drilling screw shear connector showed the lowest resistance to the applied load. This is expected due to the smaller diameter (6.3mm) of the screw as compared to the bolt and bar-angle.

TABLE I
 TEST RESULTS

specimen	Shear connector	Ultimate load per connector (kN)	Ultimate slip (mm)	Failure mode
S(1)	10mm bolt	36.062	1.16	shear-off the bolt
S(2)	bar-angle	29.075	1.12	shear-off the bar-angle
S(3)	drilling screw	24.832	0.58	shear-off the screw

Fig. 4 Load-slip curves of the specimens

(a) Bolt

(b) Bar-angle

(c) Self drilling screw

Fig. 5 Failure modes of specimens

IV. CONCLUSION

New composite column consists of two C-lipped channel of cold formed steel oriented back-to-back and jacketed with ferrocement is proposed, tested and reported. Three types of shear connectors were used to form the composite action between steel column and ferrocement namely bolt, bar-angle and self-drilling screw shear connectors. The ferrocement slab

was constructed using self-compacting mortar with two wire steel mesh of 550 MPa yield strength. From the push out test it was found that 10mm bolt shear connector showed the best behavior as compared to others. Also, it was concluded that ferrocement could be used to strength and improve the behavior of the cold formed steel column.

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